

UNIVERSITY
of HULL

Energy &
Environment Institute

DIG Planter Monitoring Strategy Report

Second Issue

City of
Doncaster
Council

NORTH
EAST
LINCOLNSHIRE
COUNCIL

Department
for Environment
Food & Rural Affairs

Flood and coastal resilience innovation programme
Part of the £100m
Flood and coastal innovation programmes

Document Control

Document:	DIG Planter Monitoring Strategy Report Second Issue
Project:	F-NEL014-5-DIG - SuDS Monitoring
Client:	Doncaster, Immingham and Grimsby (DIG) Surface Water Resilience Project
File Location:	Https://Hullacuk.Sharepoint.Com/Sites/Inssudslabuk-Team/Shared Documents/DIG- Suds Monitoring/00_General/DIG Monthly Reports/Additional Reports/Cover Sheet.Docx

Revision:	P01	Prepared by:	AO
Date:	09/12/2024	Checked by:	SJM

Description:	DIG Planter Monitoring Strategy Report
--------------	--

Cite as:

Osborne, Wm. A.* & Stuart J. McLelland (2025). *DIG Planter Monitoring Strategy Report*. University of Hull.

Acknowledgement:

This work was funded through the UK government’s Flood and Coastal Resilience Innovation Programme (FCRIP), which is part of the government’s National Flood and Coastal Erosion Risk Management Strategy for England. FCRIP is funded by Defra and managed by the Environment Agency.

Executive Summary

The strategy for monitoring planters as part of the DIG project has been built on UoH experience monitoring planters as part of SuDS*lab* experiments. For the DIG project, a new measuring system was developed to accommodate expected rainfall rates, the wide range of locations and the complexities of fitting them to school buildings. Flow meters were integrated into the planter monitoring system as an innovation, to minimise the size of the measurements system, reduce noise for classroom environments and minimise maintenance requirements whilst ensuring the system was easy to install and relatively low cost so that it provided a scalable solution.

The report contains three sections:

1. Lessons learnt from monitoring at existing locations which highlights that discharge flowing through downpipes cannot necessarily be estimated from roof size and the number of downpipes draining the roof.
2. Evaluation of the impact of pipe constrictions to demonstrate the effectiveness of existing monitoring devices.
3. Option assessment for pre-intervention monitoring of downpipes to improve the effectiveness of retrofit planter installations.

The report highlights the success of the existing monitoring strategy and identifies the need for better quantification of downpipe flows prior to planter installation to ensure planters area a suitable size for the downpipe discharge.

1. Lessons Learnt

Measurement System

To understand the effectiveness of planters as a SuDS solution, it is necessary to monitor and evaluate the planter's hydrology. This requires measurement of the inflow and outflow discharges using flow meters, and quantification of soil moisture with a soil probe at different depths using a soil probe (Figure 1). Variations in rainfall rates and the duration of precipitation events means that downpipe discharges have a significant range from 1 to 100 l/min, which presents a significant challenge for accurately measuring all flow rates. To ensure that the impact of larger events are fully characterised, the measurement strategy was designed to capture higher flow rates, from 5 to 120 l/min (Figure 2). Figure 2 shows the discharge for a given roof area and rainfall rate and the measurement capacity for smaller tipping bucket gauges (UGT, 100 ml), and flow meters. The flow meters selected have the greatest measurement range, but do not capture low intensity, short duration rainfall events which requires the use of tipping bucket measurement systems.

Figure 1- Schematic illustration of planter instrumentation.

Figure 2- Rainfall and Flow comparison chart

Downpipe Discharge

This report will examine key data from Oasis (Immingham) and Castle Hills (Scawthorpe, Doncaster) with rainfall events recorded from July to November 2024. Inflow and outflow data have been recorded at these sites. The events described are within the 1 in 1 year event recurrence interval. Data are not presented from other locations lack because downpipe discharge has been below the detection levels for flowmeter-only measurement systems.

Roof Catchment Area Estimates

The catchment area feeding each downpipe can be predicted by measuring the roof area and counting the number of downpipes, however this assumes all components of the roof drainage system are uniform in design and operation. The actual catchment area supplying water to a downpipe can be estimated from local rainfall intensity data and downpipe discharge measurements. The roof catchment area feeding each downpipe may not be equal to the predicted downpipe discharge due to roof topography, gutter design and variable factors such as blocked gutters and prevailing wind direction.

Table 1 – Estimation of roof catchment areas using rainfall intensity and maximum flow rates.

Planter	Estimated Actual Roof Catchment Area (m ²)	% of Total Roof Area
Castle Hills	~120 m ²	~25% (Expected 14% based on 7 equal downpipes)
Oasis	~65 m ²	~ 5%

In some cases, planned roof areas do not align with actual catchment areas due to roof irregularities, gutter pitch variations, or rain shadowing caused by nearby roofs or buildings. Our evidence suggest that predicting downpipe catchment area is unreliable, hence roof catchment areas should be estimated prior to planter installation. The options assesment in Section 3 proposes a simple pre-intervention test using water butts to measure downpipe discharge which would enable planters to be sized according to the expected inflow.

Castle Hills Planter Inflow and outflow

The Castle Hills SuDSPlanter unit is the smallest planter (~0.3 m³ storage) that is monitored as part of the DIG project, offering the least storage and with a design change with a rigid metal crate structure internally. In contrast the other DIG planters are larger (inc. Oasis) have a plastic crate attenuation structure (~0.5 m³ storage).

There have been 4 measured inflow/ outflow events in the monitoring at Castle Hills since July 2024 (Table 2). The events are shown in the July (Figure 3) and November (Figure 4) hydrographs for the months. It is noted that more intense rain events were missed due to blockages within the system (since rectified in the piping design overhaul).

Table 2- Rainfall events with measured flow rates with the maximum and minimum peaks.

Event	Max Inflow (l/min)	Maximum Outflow (l/min)	Peak Delay (mins)
4 th July 2024	~56	None	-
7 th July 2024	~60	None	-
23 rd November	~44	~48	110
24 th November	~100	~100	15 mins

Figure 3- July 2024 hydrograph.

Figure 4- November 2024 hydrograph.

No outflow was found during the summer events in July since the soil was dry and was able to absorb and store the inflowing water. During the late autumn event (23rd November) the soil was saturated the soil but delayed the peak discharge by nearly 2 hours (Figure 5). The subsequent event later in November had only a 15 minute delay before the peak outflow discharge occurred. It is suggested that during the November events the planter was directly discharging into the overflow mechanism since the outflow rate equalled the inflow rate indicating that there was no attenuation through the planter soil.

Figure 5- Soil Moisture of planter for November 2024. (Only sensors from 30 cm – 60 cm are in soil due to steel crate construction)

Oasis Immingham Planter Inflow and outflow

The Oasis SuDSPlanter unit is one of the larger planters (~0.5 m³ storage) monitored as part of the DIG project, offering the most storage and with soil covering and internal plastic crate. The roof is also a green roof which is different from every other roof monitored and may exhibit different behaviours since the roof is also capable of attenuating flow.

There have been 2 measured inflow events from the monitoring at Oasis between September 2024 and November 2024 (Table 3). No outflow events have been recorded meaning they have been below detection levels. The events are shown in the October (Figure 6) and November (Figure 7) hydrographs for the months.

Table 3- Rainfall events with measured flow rates with the maximum and minimum peaks.

Event	Max Inflow (l/min)	Maximum Outflow (l/min)	Peak Delay (mins)
19 ^h October 2024	~96	None	-
24 th November 2024	~76	None	-

Figure 6- October 2024 hydrograph.

Figure 7- November 2024 hydrograph.

The ability of the green roof to both hold onto water and attenuate the flow has an impact of the roof drainage times. The point at which the green roof begins to release water at a measurable rate (above 5 l/min) has only occurred during sustained heavy rainfall events/ storms.

Water is found in the planters reservoir during these rainfall events shown by the high soil moisture content at the 60 cm level (Figure 8). The soil moisture content within the planter itself is very high and offers little ability to absorb water.

Figure 8- Soil moisture for planter for November 2024.

Section Summary

Measuring a planter's hydrology is complex due to the need for a large range of flow measurements which are unobtrusive in a school environment, but also easily maintained.

At Castle Hills, inflow and outflow measurements show the planter using the overflow system, which is a positive sign of its ability to manage water safely. The planters were designed to work on equal roof area catchments. However, data collected suggests that the catchment area for the planter is double the predicted area. Whilst this is not a design flaw or installation mistake, it does highlight that roof area calculations are likely to be inaccurate. Instead, it would be useful to undertake monitoring of outflow to enable an accurate assessment of the expected discharge from any given downpipe.

The data also show that antecedent conditions are important to planter hydrology with the soil moisture being a key driver for how long water takes to outflow. The time taken for a soil to recover diminishes during winter due to colder temperatures and lower evapotranspiration. This highlights that 'design' rainfall events for planter hydrology also need to consider a lower efficiency in winter and the longer time unrequired for the planter to recover.

2. Evaluation of Downpipe Constrictions

Introduction

This section will examine the hydraulic behaviour of the current pipework setup to explore the known limitations for measuring different roof area scales and rainfall intensities. It will also examine alternative monitoring options that could be implemented across the project and their potential advantages and disadvantages.

Approach

Hydraulic calculations will be used to evaluate the flow behaviour where the pipe diameter is reduced from a standard 68 mm (and 4") downpipe to a smaller diameter 32 mm pipe used for mounting the low-cost flow meter. The calculations also include the impact of the flow meter and filtering mechanism on drainage efficiency due to their impedance of the flow which is calculated as a reduction in cross sectional area in the pipe.

Key parameters used to calculate flow within the pipe include: Cross-sectional area
Falling head (distance from roof to constriction) and Acceleration due to gravity.

The falling head will be shown for three representative heights (1 m, 3 m, and 5 m) to account for variations in roof height across different sites.

System inputs are based on roof area and **sustained** rainfall intensity (mm/hr). When the flow rate surpasses the capacity of the smaller pipe, water accumulates in the larger pipe, continuing to drain at the maximum discharge rate of the smaller pipe. The point at which the system overflows—via the diverter or leaf trap—can be determined from the height on the y-axis.

The section also explores alternative flow monitoring arrangements, highlighting their limitations and opportunities in comparison to the current setup.

A graphical user interface has also been created at ([https://www.sudslab.co.uk/Drain Calculator](https://www.sudslab.co.uk/Drain_Calculator)) which can be used to test out other scenarios and allow interactivity.

The calculations do not consider the time water takes to go from the roof to the drain and instead is almost a simultaneous transference into the pipe. Therefore, there might be a bias towards backing up/ overflow occurring earlier than would happen in a real-world scenario.

Equations

As part of the code that runs to generate the relationships, these following equations are used in part:

Where:

Q_{eff} = Effective maximum flow rate in the smaller pipe (m^3/s)

A_{small} = Cross-sectional area of the smaller pipe

g = Acceleration due to gravity

h = Water head driving the flow (m)

Q_{filter} = Maximum capacity through filter

Where:

H = Water height in larger pipe (m)

Q_{inflow} = Total flow rate into the downpipe from roof area and rainfall intensity (m^3/s)

A_{large} = Cross-sectional area of the larger pipe

t = timestep (s)

Current Constriction

68 mm to 32 mm pipe

The graphs below illustrate the effects of a specific roof area experiencing a particular rainfall event, given a defined head height.

Overflow Simulation of Different Roof Areas with 68 mm to 32 mm Constriction with 5 m head height

Inflection Point Summary for Roof Areas

Figure 11- Overflow simulation for a 68 mm to 32 mm pipe with a 5.0 m falling head.

Using the charts and interactive calculator the point at which planter restriction and then subsequent overflow can be calculated as a function of rainfall intensity.

School	Estimated Roof Area (m ²)	Backing up rainfall intensity (mm/hr)	Overflow Rainfall Intensity (mm/hr)
Castle Hills	120	95	220

4" to 32 mm pipe

The graphs below illustrate the effects of a specific roof area experiencing a particular rainfall event, given a defined head height.

Figure 12- Overflow simulation for a 4" to 32 mm pipe with a 1.0 m falling head.

Figure 13- Overflow simulation for a 4" to 32 mm pipe with a 3.0 m falling head.

Figure 14- Overflow simulation for a 4" to 32 mm pipe with a 5.0 m falling head.

Using the charts and interactive calculator the point at which planter restriction and then subsequent overflow can be calculated as a function of rainfall intensity.

School	Predicted Roof Area (m ²)	Backing up rainfall intensity (mm/hr)	Overflow Rainfall Intensity (mm/hr)
Oasis Immingham	65	175	385
Pilgrim Academy	74	220	415
Western Primary	55	505	830
Wybers Wood	57	200	425

Historic Rainfall

Historic radar data from Meniscus of rainfall from January 2020 to the present is used to look at the long-term distribution of rainfall intensities in the Grimsby and Doncaster areas. Actual rainfall data from our rain gauge network will be used for shorter-term local analysis from mid-2023 to present (except Oasis which only started rainfall measurements in September 2024).

Radar Data

Grimsby Area

Figure 15- Radar rainfall data from January 2020 to present with calculated backing up rainfall intensity.

Doncaster Area

Figure 16- Radar rainfall data from January 2020 to present with calculated backing up rainfall intensity.

Rain Gauge Data

Figure 17- Rain Gauge rainfall data from mid- 2023 to present with calculated backing up rainfall intensity.

Figure 18- Rain Gauge rainfall data from mid- 2023 to present with calculated backing up rainfall intensity.

Western

Figure 19- Rain Gauge rainfall data from mid- 2023 to present with calculated backing up rainfall intensity.

Wybers Wood

Figure 20- Rain Gauge rainfall data from mid- 2023 to present with calculated backing up rainfall intensity.

Looking at historic rainfall events we can see that water backing up occurs very rarely with an estimated probability of ~0.006%. On one occasion Castle Hills getting close to potentially overflowing (although this was not a sustained, high-intensity rainfall event).

Alternative Monitoring

There are two possible approaches for measuring flows without constricting flow from the standard 68mm/ 4" pipe design:

- Larger diameter flow meter
- Large capacity tipping bucket assembly (Only for up to 68mm pipe)

Each of these have their pros and cons which will be discussed below.

Large Diameter Flow Meter

Large flow meters are designed for industrial/ mass irrigation purposes. An example of one that could be used on a downpipe assembly is ([Click Here](#)) which has a flow rate of 227 to 2271 l/ min based on the 4" model (Figure 21).

Figure 21- Large 4" Flow meter

Based off a 100 m² roof area, a rainfall rate of 136.2 mm/hr would be required before monitoring would commence. Or for a 50 m² roof around 227 mm/hr.

Large Capacity Tipping Bucket

One larger format tipping bucket is being sold currently ([Click here](#)). It has a maximum monitorable rate of 25 l/min with an error of 22% associated at that. For a 100m² roof would require 15 mm/hr rainfall intensity and for a 50 m² roof area would require 30 mm/hr.

Figure 22- TB1L & TB/0.5L Tipping Bucket Flow Gauge

Advantages

- + The larger flow meter and tipping bucket could be installed into the downpipes higher in the head stack and is unlikely to need overflow protection
- + The larger flow meter would increase monitoring capacity for very extreme rainfall events.
- + The tipping bucket would give lower flow measurements from 0.5 -25 l/min (existing flow meter from 5 l/min)

Disadvantages

- The large tipping bucket would still require an additional overflow protection.
- The large flow meter would only record the most extreme rainfall events which would probably be outwith the design capacity of the existing drainage system (gutters and planter).
- The tipping bucket is limited to only 25 l/min and has a significant error associated with it.
- The tipping bucket would require a custom designed housing unit built for attachment to the wall and to contain the water discharged from the measurement bucket.
- The tipping bucket could not be added to outflow due to size.
- The large meter is unsuitable for planter outflow measurement due to its measurement range.
- The tipping bucket is likely to be very noisy in operation.

Section Summary

The monitoring of a downpipe for the purposes of flow measuring is complex, due to the wide range of flows expected, the need to be sensitive to the environment and the requirement to avoid causing any blockage to flow.

The existing setup at each school shows that there would have to be an exceptionally large, sustained rainfall events of > 220 mm/hr before the first overflow would occur at Castle Hills, with others as high as 830 mm/hr. Other overflow risks include pipe blockages which is mitigated as much as possible through leaf catchers and filters.

Constriction of flow (with water backing-up in the pipe) requires a sustained rainfall intensity of > 90 mm/hr for the easiest to constrict site at Castle Hills. Historically at Castle Hills from 2020 there have only been two events in which rainfall intensity was that high, with each on briefly lasting 5 minutes. All other sites have not experienced sufficient the rainfall intensity for there to be any flow constriction.

Alternative monitoring approaches could be examined at existing sites to determine if there is any benefit to extending flow monitoring capacity to very high levels. It would be best to use the larger flow meters rather than the tipping buckets. Tipping buckets are not recommended for the use of drain monitoring on the current downpipes due to their roof catchment area and that flows will easily exceed their capacity and the high errors (22%) associated with the measurement of larger flow rates.

It is hoped that this section and the online calculator shows that the constriction of the pipes does not impact on flow measurements except in **very** exceptional circumstances.

3.

Pre-intervention Options

Introduction

This section explores and evaluates methods for determining downpipe flows to accurately ascertain roof catchment areas. Understanding the relationship between downpipe discharge and roof runoff. By identifying reliable techniques for flow measurement and estimation, this section aims to provide an options assessment and expected costs for the preferred option.

Scope

An options assessment is used to look at three monitoring setups with a preferred option selected. Design setups will be created to show the general assembly of these setups.

Option criteria is based upon ease of install, ease of reversing install, data reliability and cost.

A preferred option will be recommended at the end of the report for discussion with the wider DIG project team.

Options

All options will require rainfall data captured at a hyperlocal level. Rainfall measuring can either be gathered through a new weather station or from the installation of rainfall tipping buckets only.

All options can either be configured to be either online or offline data collection methods. Due to the need to be fully flexible in the installation areas, offline data collection would be the most straightforward method allowing for quick location/relocation. **If a site already has connectivity, then the setup would default to that. An additional £600 would be added to each option.**

Option A – Water Butt

The most robust way of determining the roof catchment area/ downpipe flow rate would be installation of a water butt in series of the downpipe (Figure 23). A standard monitoring water butt could be crated with a pressure transducer and logger (i.e. HOBO MX2001), an overflow facility (up to 68 mm) and the ability to return the pipe back to the original condition.

Design

Figure 23- Diagram of water butt setup.

A water butt would need to be purchased that's cross sectional area is relatively simple and consistent for the total height. An experiment before the installation could be trialled before in which water of a known volume is added to the barrel and water level measurements taken concurrently. The water butt set in Figure 24 would offer the simplest and most adaptable design (water butt as shown would need some adaptation and not a standard design).

Figure 24 - Harcostar 227L Water Butt Set - Grey

To allay fears of potentially overflowing due to inadequate overflow pipe size (if the water butt is not emptied after each rainfall event). A tank connector can be installed into the side of the rain butt (i.e. boss connector or water tank connector) which has a flexible tube or plastic downpipe to the original drain (Figure 25).

Figure 25 – Water tank connector or boss connector.

To return the downpipe to the original condition the cut section of downpipe can be reattached to the end of the downpipe using an internal coupling joint or a pipe socket can be used (depending on pipe) (Figure 26).

Figure 26 – Downpipe reconnection fittings.

Advantages/ Disadvantages

- Water butt would need to be emptied routinely to ensure the volume required for a rainfall event is available. Overflow risk is reduced with the use of a pipe of a similar diameter to the downpipe.
- Bulky setup/ removal.
- + Will accurately measure the volume/ flow rate of water off of a roof (from very small to larger evens).
- + Easy to return downpipe pre-existing setup..
- + Scaleable to different types of pipes
- + Unlikely to become blocked due to pipe diameters used.
- + No external power required

Estimated Costs (exc. Labour and rain measurements)

Item	Cost (inc. VAT)
Water Butt	£60
Water level monitor and Data logger	£800
Tank connector	£20
Pipe	£10
Pipe Sundries	£40
Pipe Reconnection	£20
Total	£950

Option B – Flow Meter

The minimalist approach to capturing all flow down the downpipe would be to install as flow meter (as already used in the planters) to the downpipe (Figure 27). A small section of pipe would need to be removed from the bottom and a constriction placed on it to reduce to 1" / 32 mm sizing. An overflow would need to be added to the pipe in case of flow meter blockages or incoming flow greater than calculated. A leaf catcher net would need to be placed at the top of the pipe to not allow detritus down.

Figure 27 – Diagram of direct flow meter setup.

The flow meter used would be the same as already used across the DIG sites. It would however if used in the offline areas require an additional data logger (Figure 28). A similar overflow system based off a tank or boss connector can be used to fit the overflow.

Figure 28 – FMT 3 pulse meter and pulse data logger.

Advantages/ Disadvantages

- Smaller rainfall events could be missed due to flow rate needing to be more than 5l /min.
- Flow meter could get blocked.
- Leaf catcher would need to be maintained
- Downpipe will be constricted but calculation done prior can determine severity of it.
- + Easy/ less bulky installation.
- + No external power required.
- + Will not need to be emptied after each event therefore continuous running.

Estimated Costs (exc. Labour and rain measurements)

Item	Cost (inc. VAT)
Flow Meter	£250
Logger	£215
Tank connector	£20
Pipe	£10
Pipe Sundries	£40
Pipe Reconnection	£20
Total	£555

Option C – Flow Meter (Diverted)

The setup is identical to Option B however, the water is diverted into the flow meter instead, which if it becomes overwhelmed or blocked, the original downpipe is functional (Figure 29).

Figure 29 – Diagram of diverted flow meter setup.

Using a rainwater diversion kit a pipe can be taken from the downpipe and fed into a flow meter before being returned to the downpipe via a tank/ boss connector (Figure 30).

Figure 30 – Rainwater diverter examples.

Advantages/ Disadvantages

- Smaller rainfall events could be missed due to flow rate needing to be more than 5l /min.
- Flow meter could get blocked.
- Leaf catcher would need to be maintained
- Only a section of downpipe water will be diverted, therefore calculations will need to be made prior to determine % of flow being diverted.
- + Easy/ less bulky installation.
- + No external power required.
- + Will not need to be emptied after each event therefore continuous running.
- + Will act as a normal downpipe.

Estimated Costs (exc. Labour and rain measurements)

Item	Cost (inc. VAT)
Flow Meter	£250
Logger	£215
Diverter	£60
Tank connector	£20
Pipe	£10
Pipe Sundries	£40
Pipe Repair	£20
Total	£615

Rain Measurement for Offline Site

An offline site (i.e. one without a weather station) will require hyperlocal rainfall measurements. A HOBO Rain Gauge Data Logger is an offline, battery powered data logger that can be situated on or near the roof if attached to a plinth (Figure 31).

Figure 31 – Tipping rain bucket

Item	Cost (inc. VAT)
Rain Gauge	£700

Preferred Option

Option B has been chosen as the preferred option.

Reasons to not choose Option A:

- Water butt is reliant on someone emptying the water butt after each rainfall event.
- Bulkier and more obtrusive setup.

Reasons to not choose Option C:

- Unable to accurately define the proportion of water being diverted.

If feasible/ suitable a test could be attempted with a hybrid approach of Option A/ B:

Figure 32 – Hybrid measuring setup with both flow meter and rain barrel.

The hybrid setup would need to be somewhere very willing to have substantial pipework on show

UNIVERSITY
of **HULL**

Energy &
Environment Institute